

Oslo, 23.05.2023

Dear Dr Olwenn Martin,

Thank you for giving us the opportunity to submit a revised draft of the manuscript "Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies". We appreciate the time and effort that you and the reviewers have dedicated to providing your valuable feedback and are grateful for the insightful comments on and valuable improvements to our manuscript.

We have been able to incorporate changes to reflect most of the suggestions provided. We have responded to each comment individually, and the suggested revisions are shown with blue text in the tables below. Tables 1 and 2 contain an overview of our point-by-point response to all comments and the revisions provided (with line numbers for the revised text in the clean version of the revised manuscript).

I would like to inform you that we have performed a pilot focus group test. Based on the experience gained from this test, some additional revisions have been done. The suggested revisions are presented in table 3. We have also revised the timeline (figure 2 in the manuscript).

Two versions of the revised manuscript have been uploaded on Zenodo ([Version 2.10.5281/zenodo.7962800](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7962800)); the clean version and the tracked-changes version. In addition, the completed declaration of interest forms for all authors have been uploaded.

We look forward to hearing from you regarding our submission and to respond to any further questions and comments you may have.

Sincerely,

Gro Haarklou Mathisen

Table 1. Response to the comments in the editorial triage report.

<p>Comment Editorial triage of stage one submission</p>	<p>Author response</p>
<p>Objectives, context, and mode of research</p> <p>The context and rationale for conducting the research are clear and sound. This protocol has divided the project into three phases or studies. The formulation of objectives focuses on the stage of development of the proposed tools and knowledge goals are mentioned or implied but could potentially be expressed more explicitly.</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing this out. We agree with this comment and have included specified knowledge goals for all three studies. The suggested revised text is as follows:</p> <p><i>(Study 1, lines 265-266)</i> The knowledge goal is to have the expert interpretations of the relevance of bias domains and items for in vitro studies.</p> <p><i>(Study 2, lines 406-407)</i> The knowledge goal is to have the expert interpretations of the importance of bias domains and items for in vitro studies.</p> <p><i>(Study 3, lines 528-530):</i> The knowledge goal is to have a complete set of signalling questions addressing bias domains and items of importance for introduction of bias to in vitro studies and the criteria for the rating of the questions.</p>
<p>Soundness and rigour of planned experimental approach</p> <p>While the general framework of Whiting et al (2017) is given to justify the approach, the manuscript would benefit from developing discussions about current approaches to RoB tool development, consensus around best approach and the strength and limitations of the approach adopted.</p>	<p>We agree with this and have included the requested discussion. The suggested text is as follows:</p> <p><i>(Lines 569-575)</i> The approach chosen fulfils the framework for developing quality assessment tools (Whiting et al., 2017), which is to our knowledge the only existing framework for how to develop quality appraisal tools. Although, we cannot be certain that the chosen approach is the best approach, we feel confident that the methods chosen are rigorous and have been agreed upon of more than 20 experienced experts/scientists. Also, we have focused on</p>

	transparency and there detailed method descriptions and collected data (transcripts and more) will be made publicly available.
<p>The experimental approach is well described and detailed. As with all focus group and Delphi-based methods, the selection of participant is critical in limiting potential bias. A list of criteria for representativeness of the study is given. What is currently missing is a more detailed description of methods to identify (nomination by project group may introduce bias) participants as well as method to verify the representativeness of the selected experts and address potential selection bias if detected by previous. Additionally, a process to consider potential conflicts of interests of participants is not currently detailed in the manuscript.</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing this out. We agree with this comment. Therefore, the text has been revised and more detailed information are included. The revised text is as follows:</p> <p><i>(Lines 212-233)</i> To get the input we need to develop the tool, we aim to recruit participants experienced with in vitro research. For the studies 1 and 3, we aim to recruit some participants also having experience with systematic reviews, some also having experience with chemical risk assessment, and some having no experience with systematic reviews or chemical risk assessments. For study 2, we consider it critical that all participants have systematic review experience, as this is the study where the importance of different internal validity items will be ranked. Previous experience with evaluation of internal validity is considered important to be able to rank importance of different internal validity items. All groups of expected users are covered by the networks of the PG and the SAG. Potential participants will therefore be identified through nomination by PG and SAG members, who will be requested to nominate three potential participants. For each nominated participant, an overview of their scientific expertise and experience, affiliation, geographical location, and gender will be prepared. From the pool of nominated participants, PG will select participants that will be invited. In the selection process, PG will ensure diversity among the participants by including scientists from different fields having different professional backgrounds and experience with different cell culture models, covering variety of geographical locations, and having an even gender distribution. In each focus group, all participants should be affiliated at different institutions, located in at least four different</p>

	<p>countries. This way we will avoid having an overrepresentation of focus group participants from a few institutions or from a too limited number of countries. We consider that this described process will make it possible to carry out the recruitment without it being an overly time-consuming process, and at the same time secure sufficient diversity in the group of participants.</p> <p><i>(Lines 238-242)</i> For all three studies, the potential participants will receive information about the project when they are contacted by email, and participants that accept the invitation will be requested to complete a declaration of interest form. The PG will evaluate the declaration of interest forms, focusing mainly on identification of potential conflicts of interest that may interfere with the participants contribution and role in the focus group discussion.</p>
<p>Plan for the analysis of data and reporting of results</p> <p>The plan for analysis is clear and detailed. The plans for reporting are less clear</p>	<p>We agree with this comment. We have, accordingly, inserted the following text:</p> <p><i>(Lines 246-247)</i> All data analyses will be done by the PG members. All raw data from each study will be anonymised and made available as supplementary to the respective publications.</p> <p>For the focus group study, we consider that the reporting is sufficiently addressed through the following information:</p> <p>“A report of the results of the annotation exercise, as a set of excerpted text strings aggregated under code categories and labelled with specific codes, will be generated as data for supporting development of the alpha version of INVITES-IN.”</p> <p>For the Delphi study, we have inserted the following:</p>

	<p><i>(Lines 509-510) The transcripts from the workshop will be anonymised and made available as supplementary materials.</i></p> <p>Additional text addressing the reporting of the Delphi study are “The response rate (percentage) for expert panellist completing the Delphi survey will be calculated and reported. The average group response, changes in rating between rounds, as well as modifications of the questionnaire, will be reported. The expert panellists rating of the questions will be analysed independently for round one, round two, and the guided discussion, and median, mean, standard deviation and the interquartile range will be reported.”</p> <p>With the inclusion of the reporting from the workshop, we consider the reporting of the Delphi study to be sufficiently described.</p> <p>For the workshops in study three, we have inserted the following:</p> <p><i>(Lines 561-562) Transcripts of the feedback on the guidance document received in the workshops will be prepared and made available as supplementary materials.</i></p>
<p>Transparency and reproducibility</p> <p>It is not clear whether anonymised transcripts from focus groups will be published as supporting data, although suggested by “comprehensively documented in supporting data”. The list of supporting documents to be made publicly available could be more detailed. It is also not clear whether the “overview of the feedback on the guidance document received in the workshops will be prepared and used by the PG for the revision of INVITESIN” will be published.</p>	<p>We agree and have included the following information.</p> <p><i>(The focus group study, lines 356-357) Anonymised transcripts will be shared as raw data and be included as supplementary materials.</i></p> <p><i>(The workshops, lines 561-562) Transcripts of the feedback on the guidance document received in the workshops will be prepared and made available as supplementary materials.</i></p>

<p>Ethics and interests</p> <p>Ethical approval has been obtained for the proposed studies. For the sake of transparency, the declarations of interests of individual authors could be more informative and relay more information about professional activities of the authors that could be perceived as a potential conflict of interests.</p>	<p>We agree. The declaration of interests of individual authors, including information about professional activities and/or reasons for taking part in this project, are included as supplementary materials. The following information has been included in the protocol:</p> <p><i>(Lines 646-647)</i> Completed declaration of interest forms for each author are available as supplementary materials.</p>
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Table 2. Response to the referee comments.

Structured assessment	Comment number	Evidence-Based Toxicology Manuscript Assessment Report, reviewer comments	Author response
<p>2. Are the proposed hypotheses logical, rational, and/or plausible?</p>	<p>1.</p>	<p>Reviewer 1, 1.1.</p> <p>Section 1.1 Objective: “we intend that the tool be applicable (potentially with modification) to other in vitro designs or other NAMs such as organ-on-a-chip, in ovo, fish embryos, ex vivo, in chemico, etc., and chemical mixture studies”. Are these in vitro systems included in the protocol development or not? Please clarify</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing this out. We agree, and have included the following to address the need for clarification:</p> <p><i>(Lines 159-162)</i> We anticipate that the tool will be applicable (potentially with modification) to other in vitro study designs or other NAMs such as organ-on-a-chip, in ovo, fish embryos, ex vivo, in chemico, etc, and chemical mixture studies, but this will not be addressed in this study.</p>
	<p>2.</p>	<p>Reviewer 1, 1.2.</p>	<p>We agree, and have addressed this by including the following:</p>

		<p>I would further recommend to describe the target group of tool users. What is their expected expertise? And what is the intended duration required for evaluating one study? This would certainly have an impact on the design of the tool.</p>	<p><i>(Lines 208-211)</i> The target group for the use of the tool (i.e., end-users) includes in vitro scientists and risk assessors conducting literature reviews in hazard assessments/safety evaluations, which could be part of a chemical risk/safety assessment, a systematic review or both, for regulatory or research purposes.</p> <p><i>(Lines 243-245)</i> Previous studies report average or median time for the assessment of RoB of a study to range from 20 to 40 minutes (Eick et al., 2020; Momen et al., 2022). We intend to keep the time needed for assessment of one cell culture study within this range.</p>
	<p>3.</p>	<p>Reviewer 2, 2.1</p> <p>This work is part of a larger project – PARC. Could you briefly place this work in context and explain why the development of this tool a first step i.e. the focus on in vitro studies and on internal validity? Is other work ongoing to develop the other parts of the framework laid out in the Introduction?</p>	<p>Thank you for pointing this out. We agree, and have included the following:</p> <p><i>(Lines 115-147)</i> “Next generation risk assessment in practice” is a project in the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC). PARC aims to develop next generation chemical risk assessment to advance research, share knowledge and improve skills, protecting human health and the environment. The present project is included in the task focusing on facilitating regulatory acceptance and use of NAMs. PARC is a seven-year partnership under Horizon Europe, including close to 200 institutions from 28 countries working in the areas of the</p>

			<p>environment or public health, and three EU authorities (PARC, 2023). With the “Next generation risk assessment in practice” project, we aim to contribute to the development of such a framework for evidence-based use of data generated by NAMs in vitro studies in human health hazard identification and characterisation by creating tools and guidance’s. A webpage giving an overview of the planned work in the “Next generation risk assessment in practice” project has been created (VKM, 2023). The first step in our PARC project is to develop a tool for evaluation of internal validity for in vitro studies. The next steps, all focusing on in vitro studies, will be development of a tool for evaluation of external validity, creation of a guidance for evaluation of certainty in the evidence, and creation of guidance’s for the identification of point of departure and the uncertainty in the point of departure. We chose to start focusing on creation of tools for validity assessment, as validity assessment is one of the critical steps in the systematic review process. Further, we chose to start focusing on in vitro models as there is a general agreement that these are important as replacement for animal studies to provide information for hazard/risk assessment (ECHA, 2016; EFSA et al., 2022; EPA, 2018) in a wider integrating approach. It has been suggested that in vitro models could be more suitable than animal models for the prediction of toxicity. For example, in vitro data did predict liver toxicity</p>
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			<p>caused by the drug troglitazone whereas neither published animal nor human studies were able to accurately predict the hazard (Dirven et al., 2021).</p> <p>Several in vitro study designs exist; however, we have chosen only to focus on cell culture studies (meaning studies using cells derived from multicellular organisms). This delimitation is mainly due to feasibility, especially concerning the user testing, where the number of user testing participants will have to be very large to be able to test that the tool works on all types of in vitro study designs.</p> <p>The implementation of this tool might be of help to improve the inclusion of NAMs in the chemical risk assessment process and facilitate regulatory uptake, with a focus on risk assessors' daily practice and workflow.</p>
	4.	<p>Reviewer 2, 2.2</p> <p>Add some context around your decision to focus primarily on cell culture models – I'm assuming this is related to greater translatability and/or use in recent years?</p>	<p>We agree, and have inserted the following:</p> <p><i>(Lines 140-144)</i> Several in vitro study designs exist; however, we have chosen only to focus on cell culture studies (meaning studies using cells derived from multicellular organisms). This delimitation is mainly due to feasibility, especially concerning the user testing, where the number of user testing participants will have to be very large to be able to test that the tool works on all types of in vitro study designs.</p>

	5.	<p>Reviewer 3, 3.1</p> <p>Pages 3-4, lines 71-127: The introduction starts and ends with a statement that this tool is for the evaluation of the internal validity of in vitro studies, but the bulk of the text emphasizes the development of this tool for NAMs. It might make more sense to invert the emphasis and include more discussion focused on the importance of developing a tool for evaluating in vitro studies, provided within the context of the future needs related to increased reliance on NAMs.</p>	<p>We agree. We have therefore restructured the introduction and also inserted new text focused more on the importance of developing a tool for evaluating in vitro studies.</p> <p>The new text is shown in our response to comments number 3 and 4.</p>
	6.	<p>Reviewer 3, 3.2</p> <p>Page 2, lines 55-57, and page 4, lines 116-118: I would avoid using imprecise terms like “obviously authoritative” here and instead reframe as a prior lack of consensus on developing a tool with the application of rigorous methods, which is what the following sentence describes.</p>	<p>We agree and have therefore deleted this sentence.</p>
	7.	<p>Reviewer 3, 3.3</p> <p>Pages 3-4, lines 89-99: This framework would be more useful if further context is provided. It perhaps wasn’t deemed necessary to describe the other steps in this protocol, but it would still be helpful to either provide more detail here or</p>	<p>We agree, and have therefore inserted the following text:</p> <p><i>(Lines 122-131) With the “Next generation risk assessment in practice” project, we aim to contribute to the development of a framework for evidence-based use of data generated by in vitro</i></p>

		<p>refer to another broad research plan that describes the plans for addressing each principle in as rigorous a way as has been done in this protocol for #2. In particular, #1 will be of interest, since we have found it to be impractical to identify and define inclusion criteria a priori for what evidence will be the most relevant to answering a regulatory toxicology-based research question when considering as broad and diverse an evidence base as NAMs.</p>	<p>studies in human health hazard identification and characterisation by creating tools and guidance's. A webpage giving an overview of the planned work in the "Next generation risk assessment in practice" project has been created (VKM, 2023). The first step in our PARC project is to develop a tool for evaluation of internal validity for in vitro studies. The next steps, all focusing on in vitro studies, will be development of a tool for evaluation of external validity, creation of a guidance for evaluation of certainty in the evidence, and creation of guidance's for the identification of point of departure and the uncertainty in the point of departure.</p>
<p>Is the methodology and analysis pipeline sound (and, if appropriate, statistically powered)?</p>	<p>8.</p>	<p>Reviewer 2, 2.1</p> <p>Could you explain your rationale for the different sets of study participants required for studies 1 & 3 versus 2?</p>	<p>We agree, and have included the following text:</p> <p><i>(Lines 208-219)</i> The target group for the use of the tool (i.e., end-users) includes in vitro scientists and risk assessors conducting literature reviews in hazard assessments/safety evaluations, which could be part of a chemical risk/safety assessment, a systematic review or both, for regulatory or research purposes.</p> <p>To get the input we need to develop the tool, we aim to recruit participants experienced with in vitro research that are representative for the end-users. For the studies 1 and 3, we aim to recruit some participants also having experience with systematic reviews, some also having experience</p>

			with chemical risk assessment, and some having no experience with systematic reviews or chemical risk assessments. For study 2, we consider it critical that all participants have systematic review experience, as this is the study where the importance of different internal validity items will be ranked. Previous experience with evaluation of internal validity is considered important to be able to rank importance of different internal validity items.
	9.	<p>Reviewer 2, 2.2</p> <p>Will focus group and workshop participants be offered co-authorship or will this be limited to Delphi round participants?</p>	<p>Co-authorship will not be offered to participants in the focus groups or participants in the workshops. We have attempted to clarify this by including the following:</p> <p><i>(Lines 297-298 (focus group) and 542-543 (workshop))</i> No compensation is offered for participation, and participants will not be offered co-authorship.</p>
Are the methods detailed and clear enough to permit replication of the experimental procedures and analysis pipeline?	10.	<p>Reviewer 1, 1.1</p> <p>Section 2.1 Study design: I would have expected that the technical implementation (which platform: online tool?, how provided to the users?) would also be part of the study design and would merit some detail.</p>	<p>You have raised an important point here, which has been discussed in the project group and in meetings with the advisory group. We concluded that it will be better to discuss and decide on the technical implementation when we have the outcome of the studies 1, 2, and the workshops in study 3 as we might collect some useful feedback on this from the potential users and that it is important that this is also taken into consideration. For clarification, the following has been inserted:</p>

			<i>(Lines 198-199)</i> The technical solution for the tool has not yet been decided; however, we intend to make an online tool.
11.	Reviewer 1, 1.2 Section 2.22 Method: Although the protocol needs to be clear and straight (which it is), it would improve the readability if some aspects of in vitro studies would be addressed at least in exemplary form. For example, it does not become clear to me in which bias domain an in vitro test would fall which does not have suitable metabolic capacity for the specific research question it is used for. On the other hand it remains obscure to me what an attrition bias would be in case of in vitro tests. Examples for each domain would be helpful.	Thank you for this suggestion. We acknowledge the fact that it is not clear e.g. which in vitro models that are relevant for each of the bias domains included in table 3. As the knowledge goal for the focus group study is to have the expert interpretations of the relevance of bias domains and items for in vitro studies, we have not included examples to make sure that we don't introduce any bias to the expert interpretations. An explanation for this has been included: <i>(Lines 333-338)</i> We acknowledge that not all bias domains presented in Table 3 may be of relevance for <i>in vitro</i> studies. However, we will include all bias domains with approved SEVCO definitions in the focus group discussions in order to collect expert feedback on the relevance for <i>in vitro</i> studies.	
12.	Reviewer 2, 2.1 I am still unclear on how the focus groups will operate (Study 1). How will the list of identified bias domains/ items from the literature SRs interact with the SEVCO domains? Will you	We agree. More details have been included: <i>(Lines 342-347)</i> Focus group participants will be shown and have read to them the definitions for each bias domain. Participants will then be led in discussion of how the domain might be active in the <i>in vitro</i> context, with examples from their	

		have preselected example items to discuss under each domain?	practical research experience of how systematic error can be introduced into an <i>in vitro</i> study. For each bias domain, one example for animal studies and one example for in vitro studies will be prepared and these will be presented when there is a need for further clarification to start the discussion.
13.	Reviewer 2, 2.2	In study 1, the third question on “Should INVITES-IN ask users to judge risk of bias directly under a set of organising...?” may be particularly challenging for those without SR experience. Could this be altered or perhaps integrated later as part of the Delphi or the workshops?	We agree. This has now been deleted from the focus group study, and the following is included as a part of the workshops in study 3: <i>(Lines 551-556)</i> We also attempt to collect feedback from the participants regarding the presentation of the signalling questions from the workshops; whether they should be structured according to the relevant bias domains or be based on study characteristics and structured around whether the bias is introduced before, during or after the exposure of the experimental system to the test item (i.e. prior, during and after the administration of the chemical substance in the experiment).
14.	Reviewer 2, 2.3	The detail on workshop structure and what you will ask participants in Study 3 is lacking (compared to the description of the other studies).	We agree. The following clarification has been included: <i>(Lines 546-556)</i> Regarding the feedback on information in the guidance document, the focus will be on the suggested criteria for the rating of the signalling questions and whether we have

		<p>succeeded in formulating these so that it is the factors that are considered to be of greatest importance for the introduction of bias that are given the most weight.</p> <p>We also attempt to collect feedback from the participants regarding the presentation of the signalling questions from the workshops; whether they should be structured according to the relevant bias domains or be based on study characteristics and structured around whether the bias is introduced before, during or after the exposure of the experimental system to the test item (i.e. prior, during and after the administration of the chemical substance in the experiment).</p>
15.	<p>Reviewer 2, 2.4</p> <p>Why is a balanced regional distribution not required for Study 3? (Table 1)</p>	<p>Thank you for this comment. This was a mistake and has now been corrected (the need for a balanced regional distribution also in study 3 is included in table 1).</p>
16.	<p>Reviewer 2, 2.5</p> <p>In study 3, have you considered sourcing examples (i.e. text from a paper reporting a specific item) to place alongside the signalling questions and guidance documentation? In my experience, examples aid understanding and can be especially helpful for those with less critical appraisal experience.</p>	<p>We agree. The following has been included:</p> <p><i>(Lines 524-527)</i> The guidance document will also include relevant examples of ratings of cell culture studies. This will be given as short texts illustrating possible reporting in a cell culture study publication together with explanations and reasonings for how this is intended to be rated when applying INVITES-IN.</p>

<p>Have the authors specified sufficient outcome-neutral tests for ensuring the results obtained can test the stated hypotheses?</p>	<p>17.</p>	<p>Reviewer 3, 3.1</p> <p>Table 2, last row (study 1, p12): “Early study termination bias” seems oddly specific in this more general list of bias domains and it isn’t immediately clear how this is broadly relevant to in vitro assays. I recommend making this an “other” domain to cover bias due to problems not covered elsewhere, including this one, as is used in the OHAT Handbook (2019).</p>	<p>You have raised an important point here. We believe that it will be most appropriate to include all bias domains with approved SEVCO definitions. However, we have included the possibility for addition of more bias domains when these are suggested by the participants. The following text has been included:</p> <p><i>(Lines 333-336) We acknowledge that not all bias domains presented in Table 3 may be of relevance for in vitro studies. However, we will include all bias domains with approved SEVCO definitions in the focus group discussions in order to collect expert feedback on the relevance for in vitro studies.</i></p> <p><i>(Lines 337-338) Participants may suggest additional bias domains.</i></p>
<p>Other comments</p>	<p>18.</p>	<p>Reviewer 1, 1.1</p> <p>Abstract: the first part of the abstract is an introduction to the topic, which, should not be part of the abstract. The abstract should describe the work which led to this manuscript, i.e. preparing the protocol.</p>	<p>We agree and have deleted the first part of the abstract. In addition, the following text has been inserted:</p> <p><i>(Lines 52-57) This protocol describes the design and development of a tool for evaluation of the internal validity of in vitro studies, which is needed to include the data as evidence in systematic reviews and chemical risk assessments. The tool will be designed specifically to be applied to cell culture studies, including, but not restricted to</i></p>

			studies meeting the new approach methodology (NAM) definition. The tool is called INVITES-IN (IN VITro Experimental Studies INternal validity).
19.	Reviewer 1, 1.2	Section 1 and 2.1 start with text followed by subheadings. If subheadings are used all text should be under such subheadings.	We agree, and have suggested the following revisions: (Line 71) 1.1 Evaluation of internal validity (Line 188) 2.1.1 An overview of the creation of INVITES-IN
20.	Reviewer 1, 1.3	Whaley et al., in preparation: It is not in the reference list (no title, no journal, no coauthors). If there is only an intention to write such a systematic review I would rather recommend to mention it in the discussion, if considered necessary.	The following reference has been included in the reference list: (Lines 799-800) Whaley P., Hooijmans C.R., Wattam S. (in preparation) Literature-based discovery of assessment criteria for in vitro studies: a method and item bank.
21.	Reviewer 1, 1.4	“; we are not aware of a single published tool for the assessment of the internal validity of in vitro studies that follows all the steps we have outlined in our protocol” If the authors make such claims they should cite the tools they have in mind (at least the most relevant ones) and should exemplify the shortcomings.	We have deleted this claim”, as the main point is to inform that the approach we have suggested are similar to the approaches used during development of ROB2 and ROBINS.
22.	Reviewer 2, 2.1		We agree and have deleted the repetition.

		Lines 83-85 (Introduction) repeat the definition of NAMS described previously. Rephrase or remove to avoid repetition.	
	23.	Handling editor Please check table numbering	Thank you for pointing this out. The table numbering has been checked and corrected.

Table 3. Revisions made following the pilot focus group test.

Reason for the suggested revisions	Revision
Inform that a focus group pilot has been performed.	<i>(Lines 267-270) A pilot focus group discussion was arranged to get an impression of the time needed for the focus group discussions, to test the technical functions, and to get feedback on factors related to the presentation of questions and the use of examples that may be of importance to conduct successful focus group discussions.</i>
During the focus group pilot, it became clear that there may be a need for an additional meeting for each focus group.	<i>(Lines 312-313) We plan to have two focus group discussions per focus group. The second meeting will be cancelled if considered not to be needed.</i>
During the focus group pilot, it became clear that examples could be helpful when presenting the different bias domains.	<i>(Lines 345-347) For each bias domain, one example for animal studies and one example for in vitro studies will be prepared and these will be presented when there is a need for further clarification to start the discussion.</i>
It is important to ensure that we do not miss any input that the participants come up with after the discussion.	<i>(Lines 348-350) Participants will be given an option to send additional thoughts and considerations on the relevance of the discussed bias domains and items for in vitro studies to the PG by email within a week after the focus group discussion.</i>

Separate the definitions of the codes and the codebook.

The definitions are still included in table 4, the codebook is shown in table 5.